

ARABIC TITLES OF ALISHER NAVAI

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Annotation: The article examines the titles of Hazrat Alisher Navoi's works. Special attention is paid to the fact that the great poet used a lot of Arabic words in his titles. Also, the originality of the names of the works and their alternatives in Uzbek language is compared.

Key words: title, discourse, Arabic, divan, translation, addition, rhyme, pronunciation, adaptive conjunction.

In fact, since the creation of mankind, there is always a need for mutual communication and exchange of opinions. Looking at history, it becomes clear that oral and written forms of speech have been the most important means of socio-political, spiritual and educational communication between people. Arabic is one of the classic languages that has had a long history of development and influence on other languages. Although the emergence of the Arabic language dates back to the ancient past, most scholars point to the VI-VII centuries as its main popularization period. The main reason for this is, of course, that the Holy Qur'an was revealed in this language. The spread of the Arabic language in Movarounnahr is inextricably linked with the spread of Islam over a vast area. The fact that the Arabic language was recognized as an official and scientific-literary language from the 8th century that all literature was written in this language shows the process of its popularization in our country.

The art of words - fiction is like a magnificent castle. Alisher Navoi, the sultan of this huge palace in the history of Uzbek literature, like the ruler of every castle, used a lot of Arabic words in his works. As the scale of the words used by Alisher Navoi in his works reminds us of the enormous ocean, in order to progress, understand and perceive it, it is necessary to dive into the ocean. In fact, the most important literary-linguistic element in the works of Alisher Navoi is the titles. According to the tradition of his time, Alisher Navoi gave Arabic titles to most of his works. Hazrat's main divan "Khazayinul-Maani" is also named in Arabic and translates as "Treasure of Meanings". For this type of translation, the title of the work should be in the form of "Khazynatul-maani". If we pay attention to the grammatical analysis of the title of the work, both words are given in the plural form. "Khazayin" means "treasures". In Arabic, the singular case is Khaziynatun. At this point, it is appropriate to express the work in the form of "Treasures of Meanings". Already, the great poet intended to

present to his fans not one treasure, but several treasures - poetic bouquets. The word "Khazynatun" can be pluralized in two different ways in Arabic. That is, there is another form of "Khazynaatun" than the version used by the great poet, and the work could also be called "Khazynaatul maoniy". But Alisher Navoi used the first form of the plural in the title itself in order to preserve the melodiousness, rhythmic quality and internal rhyme. Also, for ease of pronunciation, the option chosen by the poet is acceptable. Because Arabic linguists consider it important to choose words that are easy to pronounce. In such situations, where the methodological possibilities of the Arabic language are used, it becomes easier for the student. And the next part is the unity of the word "meanings" in the form of "ma'aanin". The word changes to the form "Al-ma'aani" as soon as it receives the suffix "al", that is, the definiteness. These two words form a compound compound in the Arabic language, "Khazayin" means muzof, and "al-maani" means muzof ilayhi.

It is known that the work "Khazayinul-maani" which is popularly known as "Chor divan" includes four divans. Alisher Navoi named all of divans in Arabic: "Garayib us-sigar" - "Extraordinaries of youth", "Navodir ush-shabab" - "Rarities of youth", "Badoe' ul-wasat" - "Middle-age arts", "Favoyid ul-kibar" - "Old age benefits"¹. In naming these four devans, the poet is trying to express the four periods in a person's life he uses the words "sigar", "shabab", "vasat" and "kibar" very appropriately.

It is known that Alisher Navoi translated the title of "Majolis un-nafois" into uzbek in the style of "Nafis majlislar". However, the title of the work has the meaning "Nafislar majlislari" in Arabic. From the point of view of the grammar of the Arabic language, the title is an addition compound, and it is translated into the uzbek language in the form of a word combination. In this title, the word "majolis" is the plural of the word "majliysun" and performs the function of muzof. "Nafois" is the plural form of the word "nafiysatun" and is considered as a suffix. In the "O`zbek tilining izohli lug`ati" the word "nafis" has the meanings "delicate", "gentle"². But this word also has meanings such as "precious", "valuable", "high in value". The form of the word "nafiysatun" means a person or thing of high value. Therefore, it is appropriate to interpret the title of the work as "Meetings and gatherings of valuable people". In fact, the work provides brief information about the lives of 459 great poets, writers, and scientists of their

¹ Аlisher Navoiy. "Хазойинул маъоний". Мукамал асарлар тўплами. Тошкент. "Фан" нашриёти, 1988

² Ўзбек тилининг изохли луғати. 3- жилд. Тошкент. "ЎзМЭ" нашриёти, 2007

time³. Hazrat Alisher Navoi used the word "nafis", which we use today to express delicacy in the uzbek language, in the titles of his works, emphasizing the Arabic meaning, and using the eloquence and maturity of the Arabic language, he was able to choose the name of the work in a short and concise manner, at the same time, very beautiful. we will witness

In conclusion, even though the names of Hazrat Alisher Navoi's works with Arabic words and numbers added to them are called "Treasure of Meanings" ("Khazoyinul Ma'ani"), "Nice Meetings" ("Majolis un-nafois"), they are aware of their noble essence it is useful to be. Secondly, the titles of Hazrat Alisher Navoi's works have an important value due to their content and the nature of the literary phenomenon described in the work.

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